

SXC Journal of Management and Social Sciences (SJMSS)

Published by St. Xavier's College, Maitighar, Kathmandu, Nepal

ISSN:

Volume I, Issue I, 2021

Page: 19-32

Suman Kumar Regmi

Department of Management, St. Xavier's College, Maitighar, Kathmandu, Nepal

Email: sumankrgmi@sx.edu.np

Exporter's Perception and Awareness on Export Promotion in Nepal

Abstract: The objective of this study is to cull-out the perception and awareness of exporters from Nepal on export promotion efforts undertaken by the Government of Nepal, and highlight the problems and impediments that hinder their export operations. Descriptive research design has been used in this study based on primary data collected from field survey and personal interviews with exporters' respondents from Kathmandu Valley. Results and conclusion have been derived from the highest mean score of five selected independent variables, namely risk factors linked with export supply availability, affordability, export destination, participation, past export experience, and export destination to measure the degree of their participation in export promotion. Significant factors among them include export supply availability and export destination, whereas past export experience was found to be insignificant in the model.

Keywords: Export supply availability; exporters' perception; Kathmandu Valley

Introduction

Export promotion efforts are attempted by the Government of Nepal through incentive programs designed to attract more firms into exporting, such as help in product and market identification, pre-shipment and post-shipment financing, training, payment guaranty schemes, trade fairs, trade visits, foreign representation, etc. However, a glance at the data on export performance of Nepal indicates that government's export promotion efforts have not made any impact on export growth from Nepal. Some scholars are of the opinion that the stakeholders' characteristics and their perception towards export promotion play a crucial role in the degree of their participation in export promotion. Hence, this paper attempts to analyze the perception and awareness of exporters from Nepal on export promotion efforts.

After this brief introduction in Section 1, an overview of the trend in Nepal's external sector performance is presented in Section 2, followed by review of literature in Section 3. The objective of this study and the research questions are spelt out in Section 4, and the conceptual framework and methodology are presented in Section 5. Section 6 deals with sampling strategies and data collection instruments. Data analysis is presented in Section 7, before making recommendations in Section 8. Section 9 concludes this study.

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An overview of the trend in Nepal’s external sector performance

Nepal’s trade data presents a worrisome picture with its widening trade gap. Annexure 1 reveals that in the fiscal year 2004/05, the external trade deficit of Nepal was Rs.89,850 million, which increased manifold and reached a total of Rs.1,892,888 million in 2021-22. During the same period, export increased from Rs.58,444 million to Rs.129,710 million, while import increased from Rs.148,294 million to a whopping Rs.2022591 million. Thus, trade deficit, which stood at 89,850 million in 2005-06 increased phenomenally and stood at 1,892,881 million in 2021-22. If we consider 2004/05 as the base year, trade deficit index works out to be an increase of 2106.72 per cent in the fiscal year 2021/22. With the staggering volume of imports into Nepal vis-à-vis lackluster growth in its exports, trade deficit keeps mounting each year. Therefore, heavy dependency on imported consumer goods combined with just about 12 to 15 goods in Nepal’s export basket limited to a few export destination markets seems to be the main reason for this mounting trade deficit.

Data Source: Department of Commerce, Nepal Rastra Bank and TEPC

Figure 1: The trend in Nepal’s imports, exports and the widening trade deficit

As it can be observed in Figure 1, export has remained stagnant throughout the study period of 2004/05 to 2021-22. On the contrary imports have been increasing steadily till 2014/15. With the sudden drop in imports during 2015/16 to 2016/17 due to India’s blockade of its borders with Nepal, and the earthquake in 2015. Nepal’s imports have sky-rocketed during the past five years punctuated by a marginal decline during 2019/20. In the absence of any growth prospects in Nepal’s exports, trade deficit mirrors the growth in Nepal’s imports, throughout the study period between 2004/05 till 2021/22.

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Data Source: World Development Indicators, World Bank
 Figure 2: Trend in Nepal's Exports and imports as a % of GDP

As can be seen in Figure 2, both imports as well as exports as a percentage of GDP have witnessed an upward movement, from 1989 to 1997, and moved downwards with certain amount of fluctuations till 2002 on a parallel trend. Since then, the gap between them have widened, with each passing year. It appears that domestic demand in Nepal is import driven. The more the imported goods come-in, the more the preference for imported goods. This trend needs to be reversed. A closer look at the composition of the type and volume of imported goods reveal that most of them are consumer products. Hence it calls for an all-out effort to adopt specific measures to strengthen the small and medium enterprises with import substitution to produce consumer goods in a massive way.

Nepal's major import includes fuel, apparel, gold, iron and steel, machinery and equipment, cement clinker, food grains and others sourced mainly from India, China, UAE, Indonesia and Thailand. The export basket consists mainly of primary sector products such as palm-oil, soya, jute, coffee, tea, spices, etc., and related variants such as textile, yarn, unknitted and non-crocheted clothing and accessories, pashmina, woolen carpets, thanngkas, non-alcoholic drinks, plastic, synthetic, staple fibers, and others. Export destinations include India, US, Bangladesh, Germany, and only a handful of other countries, due to lack of diversification of destination markets.

In an effort to enhance export earnings to reduce the pressure on balance of payment position, Government of Nepal has raised the cash incentives on export earnings from 2 per cent to 5 per cent to exporters of 15 goods, who comply with the 30 per cent value addition requirement of WTO agreement on Rule of Origin (RoO), since 2018. Those 15 goods include processed tea, processed coffee, handicrafts and wooden goods, leather goods, hand-made paper and related products, processed herbs and oil products / precious stones and jewelry, finished goods made out of allo (nettle fiber) or hemp and mineral water. Unlike in the past where export incentives were given only for goods exported to third countries, incentives have also been extended to cover the goods exported to the southern neighbour.

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Literature Review

International trade is extremely crucial for the economic development of any country. Haberler (1959) observed that international trade has made enormous contribution to the development of less developed countries. In similar lines, Bhagwati and Srinivasan (1999) pointed out that trade does create and even sustain a higher growth. World Development Report (1999/2000) articulated the importance of foreign trade stating that it encourages the redistribution of labour and capital to relatively more productive sectors, and thus provides new opportunities for growth. There are a number of studies such as Dollar and Kraay, (2001), Khanal (2006), Hay (2001) which point out the importance of international trade for a country's growth and development.

Openness to trade has been used extensively in the economic growth literature as a major determinant of growth performance. There are sound theoretical reasons for believing that there is strong and positive link between openness and growth (Sharma, 2017). After analyzing some of the Asian economies, Pack and Page (1994) concluded that trade liberalization has provided many Asian economies the ability to move to a newer and higher level of production.

Nepal's trade policies over the years reveal that the country, indeed has recognized the importance of international trade for its growth and development, and it has taken appropriate steps in its policy prescriptions, from time to time, to boost its international trade. Therefore, the obvious question is: why is there a consistent trade imbalance in Nepal, over the years? The answer to that question lies in the observation by Paulino and Thirlwall (2004), who, based on their analysis of 22 developing countries, pointed out that although trade liberalization stimulated a country's export growth, it also increased its imports manifold which resulted in worsening trade imbalance.

In order to make course correction in Nepal's trade policy, Sharma and Bhandari (2005) suggested that government policy must focus on export-oriented industries that embodies a mix of export promotion and import substitution. This view is echoed by other scholars too. For example, Ghimire (2016) was of the view that domestic industries have not been able to take advantage of the growing domestic demand in Nepal on account of poor infrastructure coupled with political instability and lack of environment required for ease of conducting business. World Bank (2003) while highlighting a number of constraints faced by exporters from Nepal such as high infrastructure costs, delays in customs, weak policies related to trade promotion, etc., also commended that Nepal's trade policies in general were sound and that it has a competitive edge in a number of commodities. It appears that Nepal did not lack behind in framing appropriate trade policies. However, implementation of those policies needs government's attention. Khanal and Shrestha (2008) emphasized that there is a need for effective implementation of policy packages laid down in trade and investment in Nepal. They further added that it must be done in a comprehensive manner to give a boost to the export sector. Some studies list out a number of measures to correct the present external sector imbalance and boost the export sector, such as providing incentives to exporters, infrastructure improvement, greater coordination between different agencies, speedy customs clearance, better facilities at the transit points, etc., among others.

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The observations and suggestions by various experts point to the fact that Nepal's priority should be to correct the external sector imbalances, at the earliest. Therefore, it calls for a two-pronged strategy, namely constrain the imports of consumer goods, broaden the export basket and diversify the destination markets. Thus, the available literature highlights that Nepal requires an import substitution policy more urgently now, to curtail its import growth by encouraging local manufacturers to opt for "make-in Nepal". At the same time, export promotion measures become an imperative for Nepal's long-term economic growth prospects, along with import substitution.

It appears that export promotion initiatives, hitherto undertaken by the government of Nepal have not achieved the desired results, for Nepal has become the dumping ground for a vast amount of imported consumer goods. Its export sector requires an impetus to expand and enlarge its export basket, and diversify the export destinations. If Nepal's import is mainly of capital goods, and if they are utilized in productive sectors, the growth story of Nepal may be a different one.

Experts are of the view that export awareness, one of the key elements of export promotion sector reform, can be created if transfer of authority from the center to local government units takes place to make appropriate policies and management decisions including resources management (Regmi, 2016).

It is believed that export promotion brings many positive impacts on Nepal's national economy and its interrelated areas. However, the impact of export promotion in economic development, especially on business community and the business environment are not fully realized even though this sector has been adopted enthusiastically by many countries, including Nepal. Consequently, Nepalese export items illustrates that foreign trade balance of our country has always been negative and the amount of our export has been less than that of import (Retrieved from (www.tepc.gov.np)).

At the milieu of various views and suggestions by scholars, keeping aside the structural, technical and trade policies and steps to be taken for course correction to reduce the trade imbalance, this study is of the view that trade promotion measures and its implementation require a closer look. Trade promotion, sometimes referred to as export promotion or trade facilitation, is an umbrella term for economic policies, development interventions and private sector initiatives aimed at improving trade performance of an economic area. It is an incentive program, through which help is offered by the government to the potential exporters to expand their export business and promote it.

Export promotion has been defined as "those public policy measures which actually or potentially enhance exporting activity at the company, industry, or national level" (Seringshaus and Rosson, 1991, p 8)". Although many forces determine the international flow of goods and services, export promotion is one of the principal efforts through which local governments have to play a major role to augment the volume and types of goods and services exported from their areas of jurisdiction.

Export promotion is perceived in various ways: exporters view it from the risk reducing capacity of export promotion efforts, and it differs from one exporter to another. From supply side perspective, a wide range of promotional activities are conducted by the government for export promotion related to supply after

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manufacturing, wholesaling, retailing, pricing, promoting products and service, packaging, labeling, branding, product development, banking, warehousing, logistics, insurance, freight forwarders among others.

This study is of the view that unlike the other major sectors of the economy, export promotion has not received adequate research attention until now. The reasons behind the lack of research attention are not clear though. One of the reasons may be that the term “export promotion” itself is not well defined. Despite its popularity, neither the scholars nor the stakeholders have been able to comprehend and pin-point the nuances involved in export promotion.

Export promotion activities needs to be viewed from contribution of exports to the country’s GDP, and its considerable potential for the future growth of the economy. The term “export promotion” itself is a dynamic one, and it may be referred to activities to promote competence, combined with efforts to alleviate risk-aversion among the exporters, leading to an increase in volume of exports resulting in attainment of profit and earning the goodwill of the importers. Export promotion necessarily involves creating an environment which attracts a high degree of stakeholders’ participation. However, evidence indicates that Nepal’s export promotion activities are inadequate, at present.

The export promotion experience of other countries shows that even if the export promotion efforts are too little, and if they are not implemented effectively, they may adversely affect the export performance of the country. Therefore, it calls for a thorough analysis of the various components including trade facilitation efforts, policy process, organizational structure, resource generation and allocation, planning, resource management, export awareness, national export sector programs, governance, capacity building, tariff structures in the destination markets, impediments and bottle-necks faced by the exporters, transport infrastructure, among others. Export awareness and public-private sector relations are extremely needed for inter-sectoral collaboration. It is at this backdrop, this research attempts to make an in-depth study of the export sector, to gauge the level of export awareness among exporters on the export promotion efforts by the government, as well as the perception of exporters from Nepal.

Objective of this study and Research Questions

The objective of this study is to delve deep into the perception of exporters on trade promotion measures with regard to their awareness of trade promotion measures taken by the government, their perceived problems, personal factors, their export experience, issues related to the destination markets, etc. Hence, this research was undertaken with the intention to inquire into the following four research questions:

- a. How is the overall level of export awareness about various components of export promotion efforts by the government?
- b. How do the Nepalese exporters perceive the export promotion activities, and what are their own experiences in that regard?
- c. What are the exporters' perceived key problems, and what is the prospect for promoting export activities in Nepal?
- d. What are the personal factors which impact exporters’ perception on export promotion?

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Primarily, this research intends to look at the Nepalese exporters' perception with regard to export promotion. Hence, this study has the following specific objectives:

- a. To establish the general perception of the Nepalese exporters with regard to export promotion activities, based on their own experience.
- b. To evaluate the impact of personal factors on the perception of exporters in export promotion.

Conceptual Framework and Methodological aspects

The available literature on export promotion highlights that exporters' perception on export promotion is one of the key variables in promoting exports. Hence, leaving the scope for structural issues and operational bottle-necks that hinder export growth for a future inquiry, this study focuses on a select set of five independent variables, to try and gauge their influence on exporters' perception on export promotion, as shown in the sketch, below:

In terms of methodology, a descriptive research design is used in this research model based on survey questionnaires method. The main aim of the analysis is to gauge and measure the perception of Nepalese exporters on export promotion. The research method permits specialization of the dependent and independent variables and allows longitudinal measures of subsequent performance of the research subject.

This analytical research design becomes an effective tool to identify the characteristics of the target exporters of Nepal by describing their psychological factors. The questionnaire is designed on 5-point Likert scale, from strongly agree to strongly disagree, in which the option 1 indicates strongly disagree, 2 disagree, 3 neutral, 4 agree, and 5 strongly agree.

Sampling Strategies and Data Collection Instruments

This study is limited to exporters from Kathmandu Valley, who already have experienced some kind of export promotion activities. Accordingly, primary data is collected directly from the individuals through interview, questionnaires and interaction with the exporters. Exporters are categorized into different groups according to their export status, export value, export volume, export destination and other variables. For

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simplicity, this research is conducted in Kathmandu Valley, by focusing on selected exporters from different export Products.

Based on personal experience of working in export sector, along with the available literature and practical knowledge on relevant documents pertaining to exports, an attempt is being made, here, to highlight the significance of exporters' awareness on export promotion strategy, to enhance exports from Nepal. The context, issues, and challenges of export awareness, government experience in this sector and its possible impact on export sector development have been factored into this study. Thus, this study briefly points out the way forward to create a favorable environment for successful implementation of export sector awareness among the exporters.

As a first step, descriptive survey was conducted to identify the characteristics of the target exporters from Nepal by describing their psychological factors and their export pattern. Through oral inquiry method followed by collecting data on exporters' perceptions on export promotion, information was gathered on how exporters perceive export promotion. As a next step, mapping of varied perceptions of exporters with their nuanced characteristics including psychological factors and their export pattern was undertaken. This approach paved the way forward to capture the internal relationship between exporters and their perceptions on export promotion, and thus became the subject matter of this research objective and problem of inquiry.

It may be noted that Nepal National Single Window (NNSW) and EXIM code were introduced some years back. In the future, NNSW and EXIM code will be helpful to know the number of exporters in Nepal after the light flash out the number of exporters on Firm specific data.

Data Analysis

The composition of exporters covered by this survey is presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Percentage Distribution of Respondents by Variables

Percentage Distribution of Exporters Respondents by Variables					
Personal Factors		Male	Female	Total	Percent
Gender		76	74	150	
Age	< than 20	31	44	65	43.3
	Bet. 20-45	43	40	83	55.3
	Above 45	2	0	2	1.3
	Total			150	100
Marital Status	Single	59	58	117	78
	Married	17	16	33	22
	Total			150	100
Profession	Trading	59	57	116	77.3
	Mfg./Exporters	10	12	22	14.7
	Exporting Business	7	5	12	8
	Total			150	100
Source: Opinion Survey of Exporters' Perception on Export Promotion					

Source: Primary data based on Survey of Exporters' Perception on Export Promotion

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A total of 160 exporters respondent were surveyed, of whom only 150 of them, accounting for 93.75 per cent of the total number survey, responded through interview. The respondents comprise of exporters dealing with different merchandise goods located in Kathmandu Valley. As shown in the Table, more than 55 percent of the exporters are of the age between 20-45 age groups, 43 percent in the age group of less than 20, and only 1.3 percent in the age group above 45. This highlights the point that Nepal has a new breed of exporters, and a sizeable number of them are young and vibrant, under 20 years of age, who have experience in dealing with exports.

As per the marital status, out of 150 respondents 117 (78 per cent) are single including 59 males and 58 females, whereas only 33 (22 per cent) of the respondents are married including 17 males and 16 females. This throws up another aspect that Nepalese exporters comprise of a larger proportion of single men and women, who have experience in exports than those of married respondents.

It also brings to fore that more than 77 percent of the youth are traders, while 14.7 per cent are Manufacturer cum exporters, and about 8 percent of them are involved in sole exporting business.

Perception of Exporter on Export Promotion

To comprehend the perception of the exporters from Kathmandu Valley on export promotion, certain queries on personal factors, such as risk, affordability, participation, past experience and export destination were administered to the respondents in a 5-point Likert scale. The mean scores and level of satisfaction in personal factors are presented in the following Table 2.

Table 2 Perception of Exporters on Export Promotion

Personal Factors	Mean	Standard Deviation
Risk Factors	3.35	0.74
Affordability	4.17	0.59
Participation	3.58	0.98
Past Experience	3.36	1.10
Export Destination	2.47	0.86

Source: Primary data based on Survey of Perception of Exporters on Export Promotion

As can be observed from the Table 2, ‘affordability’ has the highest mean score of 4.17, which indicates that these respondents are very conscious about their financial position when it comes to export promotion. Similarly, ‘participation’ has the mean score of 3.58, which is the second highest factor in engaging in export promotion activities. Export destination has the least mean value of 2.47. The standard deviation of ‘affordability’ is too low at 0.59, which indicates that there is greater uniformity among the respondents that

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all of them are very conscious about their financial position. On the contrary, there is a significant variation in their response with regard to ‘past experience’ as a factor in their perception of export promotion with the highest standard deviation score of 1.1. This is obvious since 77 per cent of respondents are youth. It may be noted that ‘Affordability’ is the only variable which accounts for a mean score exceeding 4.

Impact of Independent Variables on Export Promotion

The impact of personal factors on the perception of exporters in export promotion can be expressed by the following formula:

$$\text{Sat}_E = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Rf + \beta_2 Ad + \beta_3 Part + \beta_4 Pe + \beta_5 Ed + \dots + e$$

Where,

Sat_E -Satisfaction of exporter, Rf-Risk factors, Ad-Affordability, Part-Participation ,Pe-Past experience Ed-Export destination

Table 3 Regression Result: Satisfaction of Exporters as Dependent Variable

Sat _E	=β ₀	+β ₁ (Rf)	+β ₂ (Ad)	+β ₃ (Part)	+β ₄ (Pe)	+β ₅ (ED)	+(e)
	=2.62**	+0.08Rf**	+0.24Ad*	+0.06Part**	+0.07Pe	+0.05ED*	
S.E	=(1.50)	(0.04)	(0.06)	(0.02)	(0.89)	(0.02)	
t	=(1.75)	(-1.79)	(-3.92)	(-2.94)	(-0.78)	(2.77)	
	R ² =0.78	F(5,154)=24.53					
Numberof	Obs: 160		d.f.=154				
Note:	*Significant at 0.01 level						
	**Significant at 0.05 levels						

The regression results from multiple regression models explain that the explanatory power of the model is reasonably high with the R² value estimated at 78 percent. The F statistics is also statistically significant at 5 percent. Keeping the other variables constant, it is found that one unit increase in risk factor will increase the satisfaction level of exporters by 0.08 units.

Similarly, keeping other variables constant, one unit increase in awareness in export promotion participation will increase the satisfaction level of exporters by 0.24 units.

In the same manner, keeping other variables constant, one unit increase in participation and export destination will increase the satisfaction level of exporters by 0.06 units and 0.05 units, respectively. However, there is no significant positive relation between past experience and satisfaction level of exporters.

Recommendations

Interactions with the exporters reveal that some of the export promotion measures can be implemented with ease through creation and strengthening duty draw back schemes, increasing the availability of credit, simplification of regulation, improving cooperation among economic stakeholders, and combining and integrating short term as well as and long-term export growth policies.

Improving the export performance requires timely delivery of goods, which in turn requires better transport infrastructure, adequate and well-equipped testing laboratories, warehouses, cold stores, simplified customs procedures, restroom and parking facilities at the Land custom stations (LCS), speedy inspection and certification procedures, etc. If there is greater coordination between various agencies dealing with exports, it will help the exporters to avoid delay in delivery of their goods in the destination markets.

Experience of many countries in improving their export performance indicates that creation of Special Export Zones (SEZs) with concessions, subsidies and tax exemptions to the exporters for a few initial years can help leap-frog the performance of exports. These SEZs can become the main hubs of economic growth.

In order to export the products from Nepal to developed countries, it requires that products are standardized, labelled, coded in Harmonized System (H.S. Code), adhered to Sanitary and Phyto- Sanitary (SPS) measures, etc., which requires experts' guidance to the exporters. In this regard, if government initiates programs to provide adequate information and expertise on the type of standards required in different developed country markets to the exporters, it will help to diversify and expand the export destinations.

The regression analysis of personal factors influencing Nepalese exporters' perception of export promotion reveals that affordability has the highest mean score, and hence they are very conscious of their financial position, when it comes to export promotion. Similarly, participation also exhibits a significantly high score. Therefore, it requires that those issues are attended to in the export promotion policies of the government.

Formation of Exporters' Association can help in sharing market specific information pertaining to different export destinations, product standard requirement, tariff measures, etc., among themselves. Such associations can become a platform for the exporters to share their personal experiences in dealing with different export destination markets.

Conclusion

An overview of Nepal's external sector, clearly points out that with the fast-growing imports and sluggish growth in its exports, trade gap keeps increasing. This trend is more alarming in the recent years than in the past. This calls for an all-out effort to revert this trend. On the one hand, there is a convincing need to arrest the fast-growing imports through appropriate and attractive import substitution measures to produce the goods locally, rather than relying on imported goods. At the same time, despite the efforts made by the government through export promotion policies, it appears that there are lacunae at the level of implementation of those export promotion measures.

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This study also recognizes that there are a number of issues which need to be addressed to promote exports from Nepal. Some of those issues include improved road and transport infrastructure, adequate and well-equipped testing laboratories, warehouses, cold stores, simplified customs procedures, restrooms and parking facilities at the Land custom stations (LCS), speedy inspection and certification procedures, etc., among others. This study is also of the view that if there is greater coordination between various agencies dealing with exports, it will help the exporters to avoid delay in delivery of their goods in the destination markets. Keeping aside these macro-issues for a future research, this study ventured in to gauge the perceptions of the exporters on export promotion at the level of exporting firms, in Kathmandu valley. The reason being that any policy, even if it is a well-meaning one and excellently articulated, if it has not factored-in the exporters' perceptions of the policies and their field experiences, it may neither achieve its stated goals nor will it bring-in the desired results.

After an inquiry into various perceptions of exporters and their different characteristics or psychological factors, and analyzing the personal factors influencing Nepalese exporters' perception of export promotion, this study found that affordability is a major factor which plays a crucial role in exports, since exporters from Nepal are very conscious of their financial position, when it comes to export promotion. Similarly, participation is also a major factor in undertaking export activity. Therefore, it requires that these issues are dealt-with through appropriate measures and amend them to the export promotion policies of the government.

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Annexure 1: Foreign Trade of Nepal (From 2004/05 to 2021/22)

Rs. in 'million

Fiscal year (1)	Export FOB (2) Rs.	Export FOB (3) Index	Import CIF Rs. (4)	Import CIF -Index(5)	Trade Deficit Rs(6)	Trade Deficit Index(7)
2004/05	58,444	=100	148,294	=100	89,850	=100
2005/06	59,777	102.28	160,678	108.35	100,901	112.30
2006/07	58,927	100.83	195,808	132.04	136,881	152.35
2007/08	58,474	100.05	237,030	159.84	178,556	198.73
2008/09	68,597	117.37	291,001	196.23	222,404	247.53
2009/10	60,950	104.29	375,606	253.28	314,656	350.20
2010/11	64,562	110.47	397,536	268.07	332,973	370.59
2011/12	74,089	126.77	498,161	335.93	424,072	471.98
2012/13	77,350	132.35	601,208	405.42	523,857	583.04
2013/14	91,361	156.32	722,777	487.39	631,416	702.74
2014/15	87,602	149.89	777,910	524.57	690,308	768.29
2015/16 2072/73	71,138	121.72	78,146	52.70	710,008	790.21

SXC Journal of Management and Social Sciences (SJMS)

Published by St. Xavier's College, Maitighar, Kathmandu, Nepal

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B.S)						
2016/17 (2073/74)	73,125	125.12	98,,951	66.73	912,826	1015.94
2017/18(2074/75)	81,330	139.16	1245,190	839.68	1163,860	1295.34
2018/19(2075/76)	97,109	166.16	1418,559	956.59	1321,450	1470.73
2019/20(2076/77)	97,709	167.18	1196,799	807.04	1099,090	1223.25
2020/21 (2077/78) Based on Estimation	112,365	192.26	1555,839	1049.16	1443,474	1606..54
2021/22 (2078/79)	129,710	221.94	2022,591	1363.91	1892,888	2106.72

Note: The export & import for 2020/21 and 2021/22 have been estimated by 15 p.c increment and 30 p.c decrement respectively.

Source: Department of Commerce, Nepal Rastra Bank and TEPC

